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“She would work out how she was going to live”: Widowhood in Colm

Tóibín’s *Nora Webster*¹

Colm Tóibín’s *Nora Webster* (2014) tells the story of the eponymous protagonist, a recently widowed mother in her forties coming to terms with the loss of her husband, Maurice, after a prolonged and agonising death at hospital. Back at home, and with all the intrusive memories preying on her mind, Nora has to rebuild her life and heed her two young sons, Conor and Donal. The protagonist has also two daughters; Fiona, who is doing her teacher training in Dublin, and Aine, who studies in boarding school. Nora’s grief and her relationship with her children become one of the central concerns of the narrative, which dramatises the family’s painful silences, their repressed rage and frustration, as well as their slow emergence from bereavement. Early reviewers generally agree on the fact that *Nora Webster*’s main theme is grief, as Tóibín produces here a portrait of a widow who, despite her depression, “struggle[s] to find –and express– her own voice and identity” (Cain, 2014).

Since widowhood is not only a personal experience but also a socially defined role, a widow’s social milieu becomes a relevant factor in the reconstruction of her own life and her confrontation with grief. As Tony Walter convincingly argues in his seminal *The Culture of Grief* (1999), the way in which bereaved people deal with their suffering is often endowed with moral significance:

Grief is performed, evoked by social context as much as bursting out from within, clear rules typically exist for its performance [...] Grief is surrounded by expectations, which bereaved people may be all too aware of, and may themselves have internalized. (120-1)

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As Walter indicates here, even if grief is a private emotion, its performance usually becomes a socially regulated act. In most conservative and patriarchal societies, widowhood is seen as a grief-related identity and, thus, it is expected that widows express their grief following the patterns of well-established social norms and conventions. As a result of such cultural expectations, the widow's autonomy is restricted and, likewise, the expression of personal urges is expected to be kept under control. In this respect, since Tóibín's *Nora Webster* is indeed the story of a woman who "comes to learn that there's more to life than the socially defined role of widow" (Boland, 2014), I argue that the novel requires to be read in the light of considerations such as the normative behaviour surrounding grief and the social expectations attached to traditional notions of widowhood and the family.

Set in Enniscorthy during the late 1960s and early 1970s, Tóibín's novel vividly depicts the social life of a recognisably patriarchal community. As I will discuss in this chapter, although, ironically, Tóibín seems to focus mainly on the protagonist's private grief, his narrative exposes how the socio-cultural construction of widowhood hampers Nora's progression into a renewed sense of self. Furthermore, Tóibín creates a central character whom he characterises through the economic insecurity and the complex familial situation typical of widowhood. Forced as she is to adjust to a new role as a breadwinner, Nora is also expected to fulfill her obligations as a mother.

As a means of contextualising the novel, I will attempt to provide a brief overview of several of the circumstances affecting the life of widows in 1960s/1970s Ireland. For most of the twentieth century, widows in Ireland have been extremely vulnerable to destitution, one of the reasons being the reduced earning power of women as compared to men. In her study on widowhood, Mary Cullen draws on the fact that the model of family that became dominant in Ireland increased women's economic dependence on male breadwinners:

During the second half of the nineteenth century, economic and social change increased the number of families solely dependent on a male wage. Suburban lifestyles were adopted by middle-class and skilled artisan families. Separation of workplace and home made it difficult for wives to maintain former involvement in their husbands' work, and very few were well placed to take over family business as widows. (2002: 609)

Worse still, in the wake of national independence in 1922, the State and the Catholic Church promoted a newly enforced cult of domesticity which “call[ed] for women to eschew public life [...] and devote themselves to home and family” (Beaumont, 1999: 94), with the outcome that female “employment stagnated or declined from the 1920s to the 1980s” (Meaney, O’Dowd and Whelan, 2013: 106). In addition to this, those women who did have a job had to face abrupt gender inequalities: “A comparison of industrial workers in 1966, 1971 and 1976 showed the disposable income of female breadwinners, both widows and single women, to be substantially lower than that of married or single men” (Cullen, 610). Consequently, it transpires that the loss of a husband –in many cases the sole breadwinner– frequently entailed a strong drop in status and living standards due to the common precarious conditions of lone women in a patriarchal society.

Even though the role of widowhood falls into the institution of the family and the 1937 Constitution defines the family as the “the fundamental unit group of society” (Article 41.1), Irish widows have nonetheless received scarce state support to sustain themselves and/or their families. Paradoxically, despite the fact that the Constitution asserts that “mothers shall not be obliged by economic necessity to engage in labor” (Article 41.2), the reality of widows indicated otherwise, as widowed mothers were entitled to derisory pensions that were clearly insufficient. As Lindsay Earner-Byrne remarks:

One of the defining features of the twentieth-century debate regarding widows’ welfare was the absence of domestic ideology, which would have logically entailed providing some form of universal support for widows. Bolstered by theories of the sanctity of the family, the judicious limitation of state power, and Catholic social teaching, the Irish welfare debates did not emphasize widows’ intrinsic rights to assistance in maintaining their domestic role in the absence of the husband. (2008: 33)

Writing in 1971, Eileen Proctor –founder in 1967 of the National Association of Widows– also argues that Irish widows can indubitably be regarded as a marginal social group, as “forgotten women rearing families on a mere pittance” and whose “value is never fully appreciated, [their] sacrifices and sorrow never really known” (2002: 615). All the adverse circumstances described here have negative consequences on their domestic lives, since most widows with dependent children had no other choice but to find

employment to provide for the family whilst being harshly judged as mothers, irrespective of their efforts as breadwinners.

One of the very few studies addressing the constraints that widows have had to confront in Ireland is Nuala M. Drake's doctoral thesis, *Younger Widows in Cork City* (1971). Having interviewed 128 widows, Drake stresses their loneliness and diminished social life, as she indicates that "fifty per cent of interviewees never went out socially at all" (124). In 1960s Ireland, the mere fact of having a social life became a challenge for many widows; a forty-year-old woman, whose husband had been dead for six years, complained that, every time she went out socially, "people would gossip about [her] and watch [her]" (113). In connection to this watchfulness, Drake reveals that cross-gender friendships were seldom approved by the widow's family and community. An interviewee intimated that a friend of her late husband regularly visited the family, but she became worried because "her young son had been asked by one of the neighbours whether he was going to get another daddy" (113). Moreover, at this period in Ireland, many widows themselves shared an internalised negative approach towards remarriage, one of them defining it as "unnatural" (39). Interestingly, this climate of surveillance and personal reclusion may partly explain the extremely low rates of remarriage among Irish widows. The 1967 *Report of Vital Statistics* reveals that "only one in every ten widows between the ages 25-29 remarry and the rate gradually decreases –being one in twenty for widows aged 30-34, one in fifty at the age of 35-44 and one in 100 over the age of forty-four" (quoted in Drake, 39). By contrast, widowers have traditionally been more likely to remarry than widows, though remarriage has been less common in Ireland than in many other countries².

In different places and cultural contexts, it has been widely observed that, unlike widowers, widows are socially conditioned to cling to their loss and keep "the husband's social self alive through memory and through reminders of him to others" (Lopata, 1996: 15). According to Tony Walter, one of the explanations for this is that "in a patriarchal society the widow was supposed to miss her husband more than the widower his wife, and her identity was usually more bound up with family ties than was his" (1994: 110). In this respect, sociologist Helena Znaniecka Lopata relates that bereaved widows, in order to move on with life, have to embark on the task of "reconstructing the self-concept"

² See Guinnane, 1997: 99-101

(120). Lopata also observes that, for widows to achieve a renewed sense of self, they usually need to create their personal space, developing new interests and friendships.

Colm Tóibín has repeatedly engaged with the topic of widowhood in his fiction. A case in point is *The Blackwater Lightship*, where he explores bereavement from the viewpoint of a daughter, Helen, who, as a child, directed her anger towards her widowed mother, blaming her for the loss of her father: “I thought that you had locked him away somewhere, that you knew where he was, that it was all your fault” (245). This conversation takes place twenty years after their loss, in the face of another family tragedy; Declan, their brother/son, is dying. Lily, the mother, now expresses her distress over her public role as a widow in the wake of her husband’s death:

‘There’s something I will never forget about the funeral’, her mother said. ‘It’s hard to talk about it. Coming home like that from Dublin and your father so young, and everybody looking and watching, there was a sort of shame about it. It sounds mad, doesn’t it? I know it does, but that’s what it felt like, so exposed.’ (245)

The rituals of mourning cannot comfort the widow; her only sentiments are those of shame and the invasion of her privacy. In *The Blackwater Lightship*, Tóibín also highlights Lily’s inability to cope as a mother, as she felt incapacitated by her grief: “I’d be sleeping alone. I’d be alone at night, and the job of dealing with you and Declan I’d have to do alone. And I couldn’t manage, you know I couldn’t manage” (244).

One of Tóibín’s short-stories, ‘The Name of the Game’ (*Mothers and Sons*, 2006), centres also on the figure of the widow and, like *The Blackwater Lightship*, foreshadows some of the issues that the author would later develop in *Nora Webster*. In the story, Tóibín presents readers with the dilemma of Nancy Sheridan, a widow living in 1970s Enniscorthy. Nancy inherits huge financial debts from her late husband and finds herself in danger of social exclusion. In order to provide for her dependent children, she needs to transform her husband’s ruinous business into a more profitable one. Nevertheless, her actions are regarded with resentment by the town authorities and the community. A local politician makes it clear to Nancy why the community dislikes her: “A shop like that, selling chips after the pubs close. I’ll put it to you this way, it wouldn’t have been the sort of thing you’d associate with the Sheridans” (99). Nancy’s transformation of the business is thus seen as disrespectful to the memory of her late husband; her actions openly defy the rules of appropriate behaviour for widows.

On the level of the family, Nancy's widowhood brings about changes in her relationship with her sixteen year old son, Gerard. Nancy is surprised to discover that her son now surveys her actions; when he speaks, he "sound[s] like his father" (91). One day, the son asks his mother whether she is going to remarry, as some neighbours had seen her in deep conversations with the commercial traveler:

[Nancy] told him it was the last thing on her mind.

'Oh now,' he said. 'That's not what I heard.' (77)

Tóibín shows here how, both socially and within her domestic space, the widow finds herself under the supervision of others who readily judge her actions and invade her privacy. As the story progresses, readers perceive how Gerard's intention to run the family business collides with the mother's desire to sell the shop and move to Dublin, where she could start a new life away from the prying eyes of her community. Nancy eventually prevails, but at the cost of a bitter confrontation with her bereaved son, who invokes the memory of his father to demean his mother:

'If Daddy knew what you were doing.'

'I said, don't start.'

'God, he'll be looking down on us now!' he said. (118)

Whereas 'The Name of the Game' concentrates on the social pressures derived from widowhood, in *Nora Webster* Tóibín offers a wider picture of private grief and family life through his presentation of the protagonist's new circumstances as a consequence of her widowhood. In this novel, Tóibín imaginatively returns to the Ireland of his youth and childhood, depicting the social and cultural climate of his native Enniscorthy in the 1960s and 1970s. As he has declared on several occasions, the writer draws here on his own family background and childhood experiences after the death of his father. Dedicated to his late mother, Brid, and late younger brother, Níall, *Nora Webster* can be considered his most self-autobiographical novel so far. In an interview, Tóibín comments that it took him fourteen years to write it, because, as he says: "The problem with *Nora Webster* is that some of it is so close to me, I couldn't put any shape on it" (Wood, 2014). Since, as has been pointed out, Tóibín's novels repeatedly delve into the psychological intricacies of grief, it seems clear that the author's bereavement in childhood has had a strong influence on his own intellectual and emotional world, as is reflected in much of his fiction. In the introduction to his edited volume *Reading Colm*

Tóibín (2008), Paul Delaney reflects upon the writer's familiar topics and rightly notes that:

Much of [Tóibín's] writing reads as a sort of displaced autobiography, as it draws on deep reserves and probes issues which carry personal significance. Illness, loss, the early death of a parent; melancholy, elegy and grief; the excavation of a hidden life or the veiling of a secret self; the politics of the family and the relationships between mothers and sons. (10)

Nora Webster opens six months after Maurice's death, when the first wave of pain has already receded and Nora finds herself facing other preoccupations, such as the family economy and her domestic life with her children. Though she strives to restore normality, the neighbours continually visit the family to offer their condolences. It is, thus, how the widow protagonist is turned into an object of a well-meaning but patronising pity. To Nora's dismay, the community can hardly see her beyond her role as an unfortunate widow, a fact which can only accentuate her grief: "She became nervous when she saw someone coming towards her ready to remind her of her loss. It was at times intrusive and hurtful" (152). A further source of irritation for the protagonist is her infantilisation in the eyes of the community: "She noted the hectoring tone, as though she were a child, unable to make proper decisions" (10). Instead of people's admonitions and condolences, what Nora longs for is a real conversation with Carmel and Lily –two old friends living far from the town–, who "would have listened to her" and talked sensibly about "the children, money, part-time work" (7). In fact, these three issues become her most immediate concerns as she tries to "work out how she was going to live" (28).

Amidst all the adjustments and adverse circumstances, grief haunts each member of the family. In *Nora Webster*, familial estrangement is intensified by a situation in which all of them are too immersed in their own needs, regrets and desolation. At one point, Nora privately admits that, as Maurice was dying, she had not "tried to guess what [her children] were thinking" (106). In fact, the experience of Maurice's fatal illness has separated Nora from her children: "Maurice had wanted her with him when he was in hospital in Dublin after his first heart attack; she could not have denied him that" (106). Tóibín, therefore, explores here the incompatibilities between Nora's family roles as wife and mother in times of great personal crisis, as she was trapped between the demands of others and her own emotional needs.

As I have suggested, in *Nora Webster*, Tóibín dramatises the newly formed gap between the protagonist and her children, each of them irremediably changed by what they have been through. Early in the novel, Nora perceives how “in these months [...] something had changed in the clear, easy connection between her and [Conor and Donal]” (17). This damaged connection is represented through the failure of communication within the family. Nowhere is this clearer than in the case of Donal, who struggles with a stammer that he developed as a result of his bereavement³. This linguistic breakdown also becomes a potent symbol of the emotional silence that dominates the mother/son relationship, as they both retreat into their pain and withdraw from others. Faced with her child’s trauma, Nora wants to believe that “it might just be a temporary thing” (80), but one year later Donal’s stammer “seemed worse than ever” (187). It is only when his aunt Margaret arranges for him to change school and visit a speech therapist that Nora realises the extent of Donal’s grief:

‘Would St Peter’s be better?’

‘D-daddy didn’t t-teach there.’

He looked at her, and the look suggested a rawness that she had never seen in him before.

‘Has it been bad?’

‘The rooms are all the rooms he taught in. I sit in the classroom he came into every day.’

His tone was direct and hard; he did not stammer. She held him as he began to cry.

‘And they all l-look at me and f-feel sorry for me. And I c-can’t st-study. And I c-can’t do anything. And I hate them all.’ (252)

Because of her inaction with respect to Donal’s situation, Nora proves to be a somewhat ineffectual parent who neglects her son emotionally. In this respect, I would argue that Nora’s characterisation fits into “the pattern of cold and distant mothers that populate [Tóibín’s] canon” (Costello-Sullivan, 20). What is also true is that, as I contend, many of Tóibín’s fictional mothers are also widows who suffer from a type of grief-related

³ After his father’s death, Tóibín himself also developed a stammer which lasted for several years. This was, for him, a “frightening” experience (Coffey, 2014).

emotional isolation⁴. Significantly, this characterisation of widowed mothers becomes one of Tóibín's literary tropes, which connects with his own childhood memories and his mother's withdrawal from him when she became a widow: "I was almost reduced so much by what happened [...] But of course I was watching her. She was rebuilding her life –she wasn't rebuilding mine, anyway– and I became interested in the idea of this sort of anti-mother" (Wood, 2014).

In *Nora Webster*, the protagonist's performance as a mother is on several occasions questioned by others, who, nonetheless, make little effort to understand her predicament. The first one to do so is her aunt Josie, who was in charge of both Conor and Donal whilst Nora was in Dublin with Maurice. During the two months away from home, the mother did not see her children, who felt abandoned by their parents⁵. In a conversation with her aunt Josie, she insists on Nora's failure to care for Conor and Donal:

'I don't know what you were thinking of leaving them here all that time and never once coming to see them.'

'Maurice was dying'

'Conor wet the bed most nights. I don't know what you were thinking of leaving them here all that time,' Josie repeated. (45)

The protagonist recoils from arguing, since she seems to accept that her children did suffer because of her absence, no matter if this was justified or not. At home, her closest family cannot fully comprehend that Nora's acquired role as a breadwinner brings inevitable consequences on the amount of time that she can now dedicate to her children. In a family reunion with her two daughters, Aine and Fiona, and her sister Una, Nora announces that she is going to work full-time at an office, but the three of them "seemed oddly suspicious of her now, as though her going to work in Gibney's were something she was doing in order to avoid her real duties" (86). Tóibín shows here how a woman's domestic role was so deeply ingrained that pressing concerns such as work and money could easily be sidelined by others. As it was typically the case for widows in Ireland at that time, Nora

⁴ This is the case, for example, in *The Story of the Night*, *The Blackwater Lightship*, *Brooklyn*, "One Minus One" (*The Empty Family*) and *The Testament of Mary*.

⁵ The practice of isolating children from their dying parent was not rare at the time the novel is set, the 1960s. In his study on the culture of grief, Walter becomes critical of "the old habits of the mid-twentieth century, when children were not told their mother or father was dying, not allowed to attend the funeral and expected to bear their loss stoically and in silence" (1994: 110).

is forced to confront both the social expectations of motherhood and the pressures of being a breadwinner.

Even if the plot develops on a domestic level, in *Nora Webster* the socio-political situation of 1960s Ireland becomes a meaningful background to the story. Though Nora does not relish the prospect of resuming her work at the office after twenty-one years of married life, her economic situation compels her to do so. In spite of her long hours at work, both her income and the pension combined do not suffice to maintain the family's previous economic standards. Were it not for the financial help of Jim and Margaret – Maurice's unmarried brother and sister–, Nora's daughters, Fiona and Aine, could not continue their studies. Thus, Tóibín's novel speaks for the fragile economic situation of widows in Ireland, dependent as they were on the support of others. As the story progresses, Tóibín also registers the changing times regarding widows' welfare in 1960s Ireland, as Nora sees her pension increased thanks to Minister Charles Haughey⁶. Infamous for his notorious cases of corruption, the politician attracts the fiercest criticism from Nora's brother-in-law, Jim. For the protagonist, however, the Minister becomes a hero who tries to save widows from marginalisation: “[Haughey] is the only politician I know who has bothered about widows” (144).

In Tóibín's subtle and ambiguous characterisation of a widow who battles with depression, Nora emerges as a woman trapped between her search for self-determination and her constant defiance against social conventions. Having passions of her own can help Nora alleviate her grief, but the fulfillment of these newly found passions becomes problematic, as they often imply the transgression of social expectations. When the protagonist has her hair dyed and tries a fashionable hairstyle, she is assaulted by the thought that some people would deplore that idea that “she was trying to look like a young woman rather than someone who was recently widowed” (53). Thus, I argue that the character of Nora is ambiguously shaped through a constant process of self-questioning and an almost obsessive self-awareness. As she struggles to be herself, refusing to perform the image of the grief-stricken widow who has lost interest in life, she is constantly reminded of the gap between her wishes and the imposition of norms of

⁶ Ferriter explains that “Charles Haughey, as Minister for Finance, devoted particular attention to widows through the Succession Act of 1965, and in budgets in the late 1960s that prioritised public service pensions for widows and orphans. The Succession Act was introduced at a time when there was 50 per cent intestacy rate, and sought to deal with the fact that, particularly in the farming community, there was often a failure to provide for widows” (2005. 570).

behaviour: “[She] acted on a whim without any thought for the consequences” (54). But, despite her self-questioning, Nora is rarely taken aback by the disapproval of others. In fact, the encounter with one of her neighbours who inspects Nora’s new hairstyle “ma[kes] her feel brave” (54).

The greatest change occurs when Nora rediscovers her passion for music in one of her first outings, when she enjoys the evening in a pub with a new friend, Phyllis. Nora soon perceives that some of the people around take a dim view of these two women out on their own, as “the older men were unsettled and embarrassed” (173). This does not stop Phyllis from encouraging Nora to sing with her, but the protagonist is too aware that this is not the appropriate behaviour for a widow. She is, once again, assaulted by doubts: “Nora knew that there were people in the bar who would recognize her and would wonder why she was singing in a pub when Maurice was not even one year dead” (172). Nora – who had stopped singing when she got married– overcomes her inhibitions and signs with Phyllis, feeling the stirrings of a newly gained liberation.

Thanks to her new friend, Nora also begins to take lessons with Laurie O’Keefe, who trains her to sign for a choir audition. This weekly hour singing soon proves to be a positive experience for Nora. Still, she worries that “there would be people in the town [...] who would wonder what was doing taking lessons when she should be looking after her job and her house and minding her children” (202). No matter how harshly people may judge her, Nora grows increasingly attached to this world that she has created for herself: “What she had told no one, because it was too strange, was how much this music had come to stand for. It was her dream-life, a life she might have had if she had been born elsewhere” (262). Crucially, music helps Nora heal herself and provides her with new interests and a richer inner life. Because of this renewed sense of self, the protagonist begins to maintain a distance from the emotional turbulence caused by her loss, as she acknowledges that “the music was leading her away from Maurice” (204).

Moreover, alongside her engagement with music and her slow emergence from bereavement, Nora begins to re-evaluate certain aspects of her widowhood in positive terms, since she can now make decisions without requiring Maurice’s consent:

She had to remind herself that she was free now, that there was no Maurice who would be [...] grumpy about anything that would cause disruption to his routine [...] She felt almost guilty as it occurred to her now that she could do whatever it pleased her. (276)

Though she feels “almost guilty” about her freedom, Nora becomes aware that her widowhood has opened up some previously closed opportunities, namely her reinvention as a singer⁷.

However, although Tóibín pictures his protagonist as a widow who seeks to reinvent herself and remake her life, his portrait reminds us of the sexist mentality of 1960s/1970s Ireland. Several episodes bring to the fore the resentment felt by family and society towards Nora’s care of her physical appearance, which surely is interpreted as inappropriate in her circumstances. In this respect, I would argue that, it is precisely through his subtle characterisation of Nora as a woman constantly assaulted by doubts and trapped between contradictions that Tóibín denounces how widows in patriarchal Ireland often “became particular targets of [...] feelings of shame and guilt about the body and sexuality” (Crowley and Kitchin, 2008: 367).

One of the main family conflicts concerns Nora’s daughter, Fiona, and her boyfriend, Paul, with whom Nora shares a close affinity: “Nora began to look forward to his visits [...] She had enjoyed his company and it was clear, she saw, that he had enjoyed talking to her too” (243). Nora enjoys this expanded social life, which distracts her from the “dullness of her own days” (263), but her behaviour raises the suspicions of her daughter. One day, when she watches her mother dressing up and applying makeup, Fiona cancels her boyfriend’s visit and no longer brings him home, which preoccupies Nora. The protagonist asks Aine about Fiona’s strange reaction, but her replies can only provoke further familial discord:

‘I think she felt that everybody was getting too friendly with him.’

‘Who’s “everybody here”?’

[...]

‘There’s something you’re not telling me.’

Aine looked at her sharply.

‘One night she saw that you were dressing up.’

‘And so?’

⁷ Curiously, this reinvention through art recalls Tóibín’s first novel, *The South*, in which the protagonist Katherine Proctor, like Nora, finds fulfillment not in her domestic life, but in her artistic pursuits.

‘And so she went and phoned Paul and they met in Bennett’s Hotel instead.’ (245)

As has been previously observed, in 1960/1970s Ireland, cross-gender friendships were socially discouraged for widows, as these friendships were often considered a preamble to a romantic and/or sexual involvement. Hence, I contend that this cultural distrust of cross-gender friendships seems to parallel Fiona’s anger at her mother, since she appears to view Nora’s friendly interest in Paul as a family treason. No matter how ambiguous Nora’s behaviour with Paul might have been, what remains true is that, as a result of her widowhood, Nora’s actions constantly become subject to moral judgement, both socially and within the family. Thus, as I argue, Tóibín depicts in *Nora Webster* the general climate of distrust and surveillance affecting the lives of widows in 1960s/1970s Ireland.

In the episode of Nora’s failure to pass the audition for the choir, Tóibín also foregrounds the social disapproval towards Nora’s care of her physical appearance. Wearing her new dress, shoes and make-up, Nora is welcomed with hostility at the convent by both the choirmaster and the pianist: “She was surprised to be ushered immediately into a recital hall” (246). The pianist, “a well-known crank” (248), sabotages her audition by using his own arrangement of the song. Not allowed a second chance, Nora is rapidly dismissed by the choirmaster. He openly insults her, telling Nora that her singing sounded “like the tune the old cow died on” (248). Considering the patriarchal attitudes that Tóibín portrays in the novel, I interpret Nora’s behaviour and physical appearance as provoking the unfriendly reaction of these two men, since they clearly dislike her even before she starts singing.

This situation is luckily reversed when Nora is given another opportunity, not by the pianist or the choirmaster, but by her singing instructor, Laurie O’Keffee. She is putting a choir together and wants Nora to become part of it. Surprised at this turn of events, Nora is grateful to her “good friend” and glad to announce that “[she]’ll do her best” (308). Her aspirations to become a singer have been finally fulfilled. Crucially, whereas in the earlier chapters of the novel Nora felt that “nothing would have interested her” (71), Tóibín’s protagonist now fulfills her aspirations to become a singer, and this clearly helps her transcend her social role as a widow.

In the last chapter, Nora experiences the unsettling apparition of her husband three years after his death⁸. Because she strained her muscles when she tried to paint the house herself, Nora is under effect of painkillers and suffers from insomnia, but her encounter with Maurice is vividly experienced and she cannot register it as a dream⁹. Sensing her niece's distress, Josie takes care of Nora and, upon her discovery of Maurice's clothes in her wardrobe, offers her help to remove them. When this is done, Nora finds a small wooden box containing Maurice's old letters. As she reads these old letters, she reflects on the changes affecting her life and shows acceptance:

She knelt down and slowly fed the letters into the fire. She thought about how much had happened since they were written and how much they belonged to a time that was over now and would not come back. It was the way things were; it was the way things had worked out. (310)

Just after she burns Maurice's letters, Nora takes refuge in music: "She sat by the fire and thought that she would put on music, something that she particularly liked" (311). Even though the protagonist keeps strong emotional ties with her deceased husband throughout the narrative¹⁰, the final chapters of *Nora Webster* point to a healthier reintegration of Maurice's memory into her present. In the course of the story, Tóibín has his protagonist gaining an acceptance of her loss and a renewed energy to look into the future.

In summary, in this chapter I have discussed Tóibín's *Nora Webster* in the context of some of the writer's major topics, such as the family, widowhood and motherhood, grief and death, and the clash between selfhood and society. Bearing in mind that this is a novel in which grief takes a central position, special attention has been paid to Nora's confrontation with bereavement and her progression into a renewed sense of self. In my analysis, I have also observed how, within this rural community in 1960/1970s Ireland, a set of cultural and social expectations limited the widows' autonomy. As Tóibín demonstrates in *Nora Webster*, moral considerations can readily repress the protagonist's

⁸ They have a short but intriguing conversation in which Maurice hints that a misfortune will befall Conor.

⁹ Interestingly, Tony Walter relates that "the frequency with which bereaved people report sensing the presence of the dead was first researched by the Welsh physician, Dewi Rees (1971). Rees found that about half of widows and widowers had a sense of the presence of their dead spouse and this was unrelated to gender, nationality, social class or social isolation. The experience was likely to take place at home and while awake. Three-quarters had never mentioned their experience to anyone else" (1999: 54).

¹⁰ Maurice is remembered in all eighteen chapters except chapter six, which describes Nora's first days at work.

desire to make decisions and reconstruct her own life, especially if she does not conform to the image of the grief-stricken and defenseless widow. Ultimately, what I have tried to demonstrate is that, by outlining Nora's difficult familial adjustments as a widow in 1960/1970s patriarchal Ireland, Tóibín brings to light the contradictions in the cultural construction of motherhood, as the protagonist's personal and economic situations hardly allow her to be the stay-at-home, close and nurturing mother that some people expect her to be.

As Eibhear Walshe perceptively notes, Tóibín frequently gives voice in his fiction to individuals who refuse to be defined by others and thus seek their emancipation from social conventions: “[Tóibín] places his protagonists within limited and constrained worlds, focusing on characters somehow marginal, uneasy with their contexts, alienated by circumstances and battling to achieve some sort of meaning on their own terms” (2013: 141). Interestingly, this is a question with which Tóibín powerfully reengages in *Nora Webster* through a central character who, despite serious difficulties, accomplishes self-development and individual advancement. As has been remarked, Irish widows –whose “value [was] never fully appreciated, [their] sacrifices and sorrow never really known” (Proctor, 615)– have traditionally led restricted lives, since most of them were highly conditioned by social constraints and a deteriorated economic situation. In *Nora Webster*, Tóibín's protagonist circumvents all these adverse circumstances and creates her personal space in which to develop a new identity, one that is not solely connected to her husband's death and her familial obligations.

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